

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for Rab3A (UniProt ID: P20336) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence

Vera Ruíz Moleón¹, Charles Alende^{†1}, Maryam Fotouhi^{†1}, Riham Ayoubi¹, Kathleen Southern¹, Carl Laflamme^{1*}, Neuro/SGC/EDDU collaborative group and ABIF consortium

[†] Authors contributed equally

¹ Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Structural Genomics Consortium, The Montreal Neurological Institute, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada

* Corresponding author: carl.laflamme@mcgill.ca

Abstract

Rab3A is a member of the Rab family of GTP binding proteins and is known to localize to synaptic vesicles. Here we have characterized sixteen Rab3A commercial antibodies for western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

UniProt ID P20336, *RAB3A*, Rab3A, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

Rab3A is a Rab GTPase that plays an important role in regulating exocytosis and neurotransmitter release at the synapse (1). In the context of Alzheimer's disease, alterations in Rab3A levels have been associated with changes in α -synuclein expression and the exocytosis of amyloid beta precursor proteins (2, 3). Notably, Rab3A is downregulated in Alzheimer's disease, suggesting its potential as a therapeutic target (4, 5).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (6-8). Here we evaluated the performance of sixteen commercial antibodies for Rab3A for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of Rab3A properties and function. The platform for antibody characterization used to carry out this study was endorsed by a committee of industry and academic representatives. It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available antibodies against the corresponding protein. The standardized consensus antibody characterization protocols are openly available on Protocol Exchange, a preprint server (DOI:[10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)) (9).

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (10).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from WT (wild type) and KO cells (11, 12). The first step was to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of Rab3A to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap transcriptomics database (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) to identify all cell lines that express the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million "TPM" + 1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (6, 9). The SK-N-FI cell line expresses the Rab3A transcript at $4.9 \log_2$ (TPM+1), which is above the average range of cancer cells analyzed. The parental SK-N-FI cell line was obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC) and the SK-HEP-1 KO cell line corresponding to the *RAB3A* gene was custom made at Abcam (Table 1) using CRISPR/Cas9.

For western blot experiments, WT and *RAB3A* KO protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with sixteen Rab3A antibodies (Table 2) in parallel (Figure 1).

We then assessed the capability of all sixteen antibodies to capture Rab3A from SK-N-FI protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a specific Rab3A antibody identified previously (refer to Figure 1) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM), the unbound fraction (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 2).

For immunofluorescence, sixteen antibodies were screened using a mosaic strategy. First, SK-N-FI WT and *RAB3A* KO cells were labelled with different fluorescent dyes in order to distinguish the two cell lines, and the Rab3A antibodies were evaluated. Both WT and KO lines were imaged in the same field of view to reduce staining, imaging and image analysis bias (Figure 3). Quantification of immunofluorescence intensity in hundreds of WT and KO cells was performed for each antibody tested, and the images presented in Figure 3 are representative of this analysis.

In conclusion, we have screened sixteen Rab3A commercial antibodies by western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human SK-N-FI WT and *RAB3A* KO cells. To assist viewers in interpreting antibody performance, Table 3 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications. Several high-quality and renewable Rab3A antibodies were identified in all applications. Researchers who wish to study Rab3A in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality and renewable antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available Rab3A antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts on the Rab family of proteins or vesicle trafficking, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. Rab3A experts are responsible for analyzing and interpreting observed banding patterns in western blots and subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In immunofluorescence, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results (13). Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Methods

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocol Exchange, a preprint server (DOI: [10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)) (9). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup relevant to this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies used

Cell lines used and primary antibodies tested in this study are listed in Table 1 and 2, respectively. To ensure that the cell lines and antibodies are cited properly and can be easily identified, we have included their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers, or RRID (14, 15). SK-HEP-1 KO clone corresponding to the *RAB3A* gene was generated with low passage cells at Abcam. Two guide RNAs were used to introduce a deletion in Exon 3 of the *RAB3A* gene (sequence guide 1: TGCATTGAAGGATTCCTCGT, sequence guide 2: AGTATGCGGTGGTGATGGTC). Cells were cultured in RPMI 1640 (Gibco, cat. number A1049101) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 0.05 mM 2-Mercaptoethanol (Gibco, cat. number 21985023, 2 mM L-glutamine (Wisent cat. number 609-065), 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201). Secondary antibodies Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse are (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520) and Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse secondary antibodies (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A21429 and A21424) were used. Protein A:HRP from MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8651 was used as a secondary system to detect the IPs.

Antibody screening by western blot

SK-HEP-1 WT and *RAB3A* KO cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WG1201BOX) ran with MES SDS buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), loaded in LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated overnight at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20

(TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) Or Clarity Western ECL Substrate (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg or 10 µl of antibody ab234089* as the concentration is unknown to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 hr at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

SK-HEP-1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked for 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 $\times g$ for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on a precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels. Protein A: HRP was used as a secondary antibody at a dilution of 2 µg/ml.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

SK-HEP-1 WT and *RAB3A* KO cells labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number C2925 and C34565, respectively). WT and KO cells were plated in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom. (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator, 37°C, 5% CO₂. Cells were fixed in 4% PFA (in PBS) for 15 min at room temperature and then washed 3 times with PBS. Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary STING1 antibodies overnight at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 \times 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/ml for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 \times 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68

x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification (16). Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

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Competing interests

For this project, the laboratory of Peter McPherson developed partnerships with high-quality antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to the McPherson laboratory at no cost. These partners include: - Abcam- ABCD antibodies- ABclonal- Aviva Systems Biology -Bio Techne -Cell Signalling Technology -Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank - GeneTex – Horizon Discovery – Proteintech – Synaptic Systems –Thermo Fisher Scientific.

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Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
ATCC	CRL-2142	CVCL_1702	SK-N-FI	WT
Abcam	not available	not available	SK-N-FI	<i>RAB3A</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the Rab3A antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab234089*	1014328-1	AB_3096334	monoclonal	6D1A12	mouse	n/a	Wb
Abcam	ab285163**	GR3412273-1	AB_3099448	recombinant-mono	EPR24450-44	rabbit	0.47	Wb, IP
Abcam	ab302518**	1006622-1	AB_3099464	recombinant-mono	EPR26022-9	rabbit	0.55	Wb, IP, IF
Abcam	ab3335	GR3383095-2	AB_303714	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF
Abcam	ab80192	GR2245622	AB_2042751	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.10	Wb, IF
Abclonal	A5379	1158030101	AB_2766189	polyclonal	-	rabbit	2.79	Wb, IF
Bio-Techne	NBP2-45499*	F001	AB_3096329	monoclonal	OTI1G3	mouse	1.00	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	12214**	1	AB_2797847	recombinant-mono	D7B10	rabbit	0.10	Wb
GeneTex	GTX77706	822104494	AB_424654	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb
Proteintech	15029-1-AP	6116	AB_2177378	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.37	Wb, IP
Synaptic Systems	107 102	107102/3	AB_887769	polyclonal	-	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IP, IF
Synaptic Systems	107 111*	1. - 21	AB_2619776	monoclonal	42.2	mouse	1.00	Wb, IP, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-27162*	WI3378397	AB_2725178	monoclonal	OTI1G3	mouse	1.00	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-27178*	WI3378398	AB_2725179	monoclonal	OTI5C12	mouse	1.00	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-37684*	WI3377721A	AB_2897608	monoclonal	1531CT562.14.57	mouse	0.50	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-49607**	H681506005	AB_3094127	recombinant-mono	PSH01-08	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IF

Wb=Western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP=immunoprecipitation, *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody, n/a=not available

Table 3: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Western blot			Immunoprecipitation			Immunofluorescence		
Successful antibody	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody	Successful antibody	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody	WT/KO cell mosaic	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody
WT KO	WT KO	WT KO	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	WT KO	WT KO	WT KO
<p>Target protein not detected</p>								

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Figure 1: Rab3A antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: Rab3A antibody screening by immunoprecipitation (1/2)

Figure 2: Rab3A antibody screening by immunoprecipitation (2/2)

Figure 3: RAB3A antibody screening by immunofluorescence

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: Rab3A antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of SK-N-FI WT and *RAB3A* KO were prepared, and 40 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated Rab3A antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Exceptions were given for antibodies ab234089*, ab285163**, NBP2-45499*, MA5-27178* and MA5-49607** which were titrated as the signal was too weak when following the supplier's recommendations. Antibody dilution used: ab234089* at 1/200, ab285163** at 1/200, ab302518** at 1/1000, ab3335 at 1/1000, ab80192 at 1/200, A5379 at 1/1000, NBP2-45499* at 1/1000, 12214** at 1/1000, GTX77706 at 1/200, 15029-1-AP at 1/1000, 107 102 at 1/1000, 107 111* at 1/1000, MA5-27162* at 1/1000, MA5-27178* at 1/200, MA5-37684* at 1/1000 and MA5-49607** at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 25 kDa. *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody.

Figure 2: Rab3A antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

SK-N-FI lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 1 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated Rab3A antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. The concentration of ab234089* is unknown and therefore 10 µl of antibody were used for this test. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the indicated Rab3A antibody. For western blot, antibodies MA5-49607** and 12214** were used at 1/1000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate, *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody.

Figure 3: Rab3A antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

SK-N-FI WT and *RAB3A* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio on coverslips. Cells were stained with the indicated Rab3A antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (WT), red (antibody staining) and far-red (KO) channels was performed. Representative images of the merged blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. When an antibody was recommended for immunofluorescence by the supplier, we tested it at the recommended dilution. The rest of the antibodies were tested at 1 and 2 µg/mL and the final concentration was selected based on the detection range of the microscope used and a quantitative analysis not shown here. Antibody dilution used: ab234089* at 1/1000, ab285163** at 1/500, ab302518** at 1/500, ab3335 at 1/1000, ab80192 at 1/50, A5379 at 1/50, NBP2-45499* at 1/150, 12214** at 1/50, GTX77706 at 1/500, 15029-1-AP at 1/400, 107 102 at 1/500, 107 111* at 1/1000, MA5-27162* at 1/150, MA5-27178* at 1/150, MA5-37684* at 1/25 and MA5-49607** at 1/1000. Bars = 10 µm. *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody.